

Reversed phase thin layer chromatography of amino acids on silicone fluid DC200, triaryl phosphate and tri-*n*-butylamine impregnated silica gel-G layers

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Manuscript received 6 September 2002, revised 11 February 2003, accepted 4 March 2003

Chromatographic behaviour of twentyfour amino acids has been studied on silicone fluid DC200, triaryl phosphate (TAP) and tri-*n*-butylamine (TBA) impregnated silica gel-G layers in two-component mobile phases (*n*-propanol-water) in varying ratios. The effect of impregnation, mobile phase composition and the effect of solubility on hR_F of amino acids are discussed. The mechanism of migration is explained in terms of adsorption on impregnated silica gel-G and polarity of the mobile phase used.

Silicone fluid DC200 has been used as impregnant for silica gel-G layers in the separation of quinolone derivatives¹. Similarly tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) and tri-*n*-butylamine (TBA) have been used as impregnants for silica gel-G layers in the qualitative and quantitative separation of metal ions². Recently, silicone fluid DC200, triaryl phosphate and tri-*n*-butylamine impregnated silica gel-GF₂₅₄ has successfully been used for the separation of 3d-metal ions³.

However, no effort has ever been made for the reversed phase thin layer chromatography (RPTLC) of amino acids on silicone fluid DC200 and triaryl phosphate (TAP) impregnated silica gel-G layers using *n*-propanol-water as mobile phase. Tri-*n*-butylamine is also used as an impregnant in order to compare the effect of alkyl and aryl groups on the RPTLC behaviour of amino acids. The effect of mobile phase composition is also studied.

Results and discussion

In the RPTLC of amino acids on silicone fluid DC200, TAP and TBA impregnated silica gel-G layers in *n*-propanol-water mobile phases, most of the spots are well defined and compact and tailing is observed only for few amino acids. Earlier *n*-propanol-water (7 : 3) mobile phase has been very useful in the separation of amino acids on KC₁₈ silica gel-G and other reversed phase thin layers⁴. The results are reproducible and the variation in the R_F does not exceed 10% of the average value.

In general, all the neutral and acidic amino acids show higher R_F irrespective of the level of impregnation. Basic amino acids exhibit lower R_F on impregnated layers which may be due to the presence of lone pair of electrons on the extra NH₂ group. However, the relatively higher R_F of L-lysineHCl is probably due to it being least basic among

basic amino acids. L-Arginine is strongly basic in nature due to the presence of guanidino group in its molecule and as such its R_F is very low.

Effect of impregnation :

In order to study the effect of impregnation, plots of R_F vs percentage impregnation were drawn for all the amino acids (Figs. not shown) which led to the following conclusions :

(A) Effect of impregnation with silicone fluid DC200 :

Generally, all the neutral and acidic amino acids show higher and constant R_F irrespective of the percentage impregnation except for DL-alanine, DL-2-amino butyric acid, DL-serine, DL- β -phenyl alanine, DL-methionine, L-tyrosine, DL-DOPA (dihydroxy-phenyl-alanine) and L-cystine which show a sudden change in their R_F in the 4–6% impregnation range. Upto 4% impregnation, DL-alanine shows a gradual increase in its R_F which decreases on further increase in percentage impregnation. However, DL-serine and L-cystine exhibit decrease in R_F with an increase in percentage impregnation upto 4% impregnation, which may be due to strong adsorption of the acids. The R_F , then, suddenly increases at 6% impregnation, suggesting that the two acids are selectively adsorbed on 4% impregnated layers. At 6% impregnation, DL-2-amino butyric acid, DL-methionine, L-tyrosine and DL-DOPA show a sudden fall in their R_F probably due to their higher adsorption. For DL-methionine, lower R_F may be due to the presence of sulfur in its molecule which possesses two extra lone pairs of electrons and is also attached to the methyl groups which has the electron donating nature. Consequently, the electron density around the sulfur atom increases due to which some specific interaction takes place between the impregnated layer and the

amino acid resulting in much lower R_F . Similarly L-tyrosine and DL-DOPA show lower R_F due to the presence of phenyl group in their molecule causing higher molecular mass and as such these acids are strongly adsorbed resulting in lower R_F . However, for basic amino acids the lower and constant R_F is observed at each level of impregnation except for L-lysineHCl which shows higher R_F on 2, 4 and 8% impregnated layers. L-LysineHCl, being least basic is loosely held up by the surface resulting in higher R_F . On 6% impregnated layers, due to some specific interaction, the acid is strongly adsorbed giving lower R_F . Thus, due to this anomalous behaviour, the separation possibilities are higher which have actually been realized as given in Table 1.

However, the $R_F \geq 0.40$ which may be due to the solvation of these amino acids by the mobile phase used. L-Leucine shows higher and constant R_F upto 4% impregnation and then a sudden decrease in R_F is noticed at the level of 6% impregnation probably due to the higher adsorption owing to significant decrease in the polarity of the adsorbent layer. In case of DL-nor leucine, the R_F value gradually increases upto 4% impregnation. Beyond this, the effect of impregnation is negligible resulting in almost constant R_F . DL-Tryptophan shows gradual decrease in R_F upto 6% impregnation and then onwards the R_F becomes almost constant. The initial decrease in R_F may be attributed to its higher molecular mass.

Table 1. Separations achieved on impregnated silica gel-G layers

Impregnating material	Mobile phase used	Separations achieved
2% Silicone fluid DC200	M ₇	Arg and Orn from <i>n</i> -But or Pro or Ile or Tyr or DOPA or Asp
4% Silicone fluid DC200	M ₇	Arg and Asp from Hyd or Leu or Trp
4% Silicone fluid DC200	M ₄	Arg and Orn from Ser or Cyst or Met or β -Phe or Cys or Glu
4% Silicone fluid DC200 Hyd	M ₅	Arg and Orn from Gly or Ser or Val or Leu
4% Silicone fluid DC200	M ₆	His, and <i>n</i> -Leu from Gly or Hyd or <i>n</i> -But or Ser or Pro or Thr or Cyst or Ile or Met or Try
6% Silicone fluid DC200	M ₇	Cyst from Ser or Val or Leu or β -Phe
2% TAP	M ₇	Arg and Orn from Ala or Thr or DOPA
4% TAP	M ₇	Ala from Gly or Hyd or <i>n</i> -But or Ser or Thr or Cyst or Try or Cys or Lys or Asp
2% TBA	M ₇	Arg and Orn from Lys
4% TBA	M ₇	Arg and Orn from Try

(B) Effect of impregnation with TAP :

On TAP impregnated layers, neutral amino acids such as L-hydroxy proline, DL-alanine, L-leucine, DL-iso leucine, DL-nor leucine and DL-tryptophan show a sudden change in their R_F with an increase in % age impregnation. L-Hydroxy proline and DL-alanine show an increase in their R_F on these layers having upto 4% impregnation. On further increase in percentage impregnation, the R_F gradually decreases. Due to the decrease in the polarity of the surface.

The behaviour of basic amino acids on these layers is almost similar as on silicone fluid DC200 impregnated layers. L-OrnithineHCl, L-histidineHCl and L-arginine do not show significant variation in their R_F with increasing level of impregnation. It is important to note that the solubility of L-histidineHCl, a basic amino acid is much lower in alcohol-water mobile phase⁵. It is, thus, presumed that the solubilities of other amino acids will also be lower in the given mobile phase. Further, L-arginine shows very low R_F probably due to the presence of guanidino group in its molecule due to which it is much less soluble in the given mobile phase. Thus, the lower R_F may be due to the lower solubility of these acids in the mobile phase. However, L-lysineHCl shows different behaviour due to the presence of larger aliphatic side chain in it, which decreases the polar nature of the acid due to which it is less adsorbed causing higher R_F .

(C) Effect of impregnation with TBA :

In general, all neutral amino acids exhibit slight decrease in R_F with an increase in the percentage TBA impregnation upto the level of 6%. This decrease in R_F is probably due to the gradual increase in the non-polar nature of the layer surface. However, beyond this level of impregnation, the R_F remains almost constant suggesting that the layer has become almost non-polar even at 6% TBA impregnation and further increase in percentage impregnation does not effect the nature of the layer surface significantly. In general, the basic amino acids are strongly adsorbed on TBA impregnated layers causing lower R_F . No effect of change of percentage impregnation is observed on the migration of these acids. However, L-lysineHCl shows higher R_F at each level of impregnation and is separated from other basic amino acids.

Effect of mobile phase composition on R_F :

In order to study the effect of mobile phase composition on R_F for various amino acids using 4% silicone fluid DC200

and TAP impregnated silica gel-G layers, plots of R_F vs mobile phase composition were drawn. The salient features are :

(A) On silicone fluid DC200 impregnated layers :

The R_F values of all the neutral and acidic amino acids are higher and almost constant suggesting that, there is no significant effect of mobile phase composition on R_F . The R_F value of L-hydroxy proline, L-proline, L-leucine and DL-nor leucine gradually decreases only upto the mobile phase composition 4 : 6. It may be due to the slight decrease in the polar nature of the mobile phase. However, in case of basic amino acids, the R_F value gradually decreases with an increase in the *n*-propanol ratio in the mobile phase. The *n*-propanol is less polar than water, and thus due to the increase in its percentage the polarity of the mobile phase decreases. Unlike other basic amino acids L-arginine shows a sudden fall in its R_F beyond mobile phase composition 2 : 8 which continues till it becomes zero at the mobile phase composition 8 : 2. The decrease in R_F may be because of an increase in the proportion of *n*-propanol in the mobile phase and also to its higher pK_2 and pK_3 values as compared to other basic amino acids. In *n*-propanol, the R_F of basic amino acid is either very low or zero because of very low solubility in it.

(B) On TAP impregnated layers :

The neutral and acidic amino acids show higher and constant R_F on these layers except in case of DL-valine, DL-methionine and DL-DOPA, which show a gradual increase in R_F upto the composition 4 : 6 and beyond which the R_F decreases. However, the basic amino acids show a gradual decrease in their R_F with an increase in the proportion of *n*-propanol in the mobile phase and becomes zero in *n*-propanol. Interestingly, L-lysineHCl shows a different trend as the R_F value decreases to a much lesser extent and significantly higher R_F (0.6) is observed even in *n*-propanol. This may be due to relatively higher solubility of L-lysineHCl in *n*-propanol. L-OrnithineHCl exhibits abnormal behaviour and no definite trend in R_F is noticed.

In case of water as mobile phase, the R_F of almost all amino acids is higher on silicone fluid DC200 impregnated layers as compared to the values on TAP impregnated ones. This is due to the fact that TAP impregnated layers are slightly polar whereas silicone fluid DC200 impregnated layer are almost non-polar. The slightly lower R_F on TAP impregnated layers is due to the polar-polar interactions which decrease the R_F to a considerable extent in case of some of the amino acids.

Effect of solubility on hR_F values of amino acids :

A mechanism of migration based on solubility in

n-propanol-water mobile phase is considered. The solubilities of some amino acids such as L-tyrosine, L-histidineHCl, L-leucine, DL- β -phenylalanine and DL-tryptophan in 60% alcohol-water and are given as 0.02, 0.5, 0.62, 1.23 and 1.40 g/100 g respectively⁵. For these acids, a plot of hR_F vs solubility in 60% alcohol-water mixture reveals that on unimpregnated silica gel-G layers, higher and constant hR_F value (≥ 0.80) for all acids except L-histidine is observed irrespective of the remarkable difference in their solubilities. Thus, the hR_F of these acids is independent of solubility factor. However, the much lower hR_F for L-histidine HCl is due to its basic nature and its solubility does not appear to be the deciding factor.

In case of impregnated layers, the hR_F of the amino acids gradually increases with an increase in the solubility in the range 0.02 to 0.6. However, beyond this, the hR_F is independent of solubility factor as it remains almost constant even when there is more than two fold increase in the solubility.

Separation of L-arginine from other amino acids :

To assess the separation of L-arginine (basic amino acid) from other amino acid on 4% silicone fluid DC200 impregnated silica gel-G layers in *n*-propanol-water (6 : 4) mobile phase, the TLC parameters ΔhR_F (hR_F of separated amino acids $-hR_F$ of L-arginine) and the separation factor (α) are calculated. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameters for the separation of Arg from some other amino acids on 4% silicone fluid DC200 impregnated silica gel-G layers using *n*-propanol-water (6 : 4) as mobile phase

Sl. no.	Separated amino acids	TLC parameters	
		ΔhR_F	α
1.	Arg-Gly	70	81.8
2.	Arg-Hyd	52	52.9
3.	Arg- <i>n</i> -But	72	42.8
4.	Arg-Ser	80	81.8
5.	Arg-Pro	85	180.0
6.	Arg-Thr	70	36.0
7.	Arg-Cyst	75	52.9
8.	Arg-Leu	72	42.8
9.	Arg-Ile	70	36.0
10.	Arg-Met	82	112.5
11.	Arg-Tyr	85	60.0
12.	Arg- β -Phe	75	52.9
13.	Arg-Trp	70	36.0
14.	Arg-Cys	80	81.8
15.	Arg-Asp	62	23.6
16.	Arg-Glu	75	52.9
17.	Arg-DOPA	85	180.0

The interesting feature of the above study is that a large number of amino acid separations on different impregnated layers are achieved as reported in Table 1.

Experimental

Silicone fluid DC200 (B.D.H.), TAP (FMC-corporation), TBA (LOBA), silica gel-G (E. Merck) and *n*-propanol (Qualigens) were used. Test solutions and detector were prepared as reported earlier⁶.

Preparation of chromatoplates and chromatographic procedure are same as reported earlier⁷. The mobile phases used are : *n*-propanol-water in the proportions, 0 : 10 (M₁); 2 : 8 (M₂); 4 : 6 (M₃); 6 : 4 (M₄); 8 : 2 (M₅); 10 : 0 (M₆) and 7 : 3 (M₇).

The amino acids used were glycine (Gly), hydroxy proline (Hyd), alanine (Ala), 2-amino butyric acid (*n*-But), serine (Ser), proline (Pro), valine (Val), threonine (Thr), cysteine (Cyst), leucine (Leu), iso-leucine (Ile), nor leucine (*n*-Leu), methionine (Met), tyrosine (Tyr), β -phenyl alanine (β -phe), tryptophan (Trp), dihydroxy phenyl alanine (DOPA), cystine (Cys), ornithine (Orn), lysine (Lys), histidine (His), arginine (Arg), aspartic acid (Asp) and glutamic

acid (Glu).

The chromatograms were dried in oven at 100° and then spots detected with 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone. The chromatograms were kept in oven at 100° for 5–10 min so that spots are visualized clearly.

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